

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Enhancing mental well-being for parents through competence based curriculum implementation strategies in public day primary schools in Nairobi County, Kenya

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Abstract

The Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) focuses on developing learners' skills and competencies, ensuring a holistic approach to education. Active parental engagement in their children's education is essential, as it not only enhances the academic success of learners but also significantly contributes to the mental well-being of parents. This study aims to explore strategies that may enhance the mental well-being of parents during CBC implementation in public day schools primary in Nairobi County, Kenya. The study adopted a qualitative design and was grounded in the theory of the Epstein model and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. The target population comprised parents of children enrolled in public day primary schools in Nairobi County. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select a sample size of 12 participants, ensuring a representative distribution across different demographic profiles. Data was collected using in-depth interviews and subjected to thematic analysis. The findings revealed that enhancing parental support during CBC implementation requires a multifaceted approach involving workshops, accessible resources, effective communication, and collaboration from schools. Schools should provide training sessions and online materials to guide parents through the CBC framework while maintaining regular updates on curriculum changes. Additionally, parents' associations may foster community support groups and offer mental health resources, which can alleviate stress for parents. The study also emphasized the role of learners in supporting their parents through effective communication and encouraging independence, promoting a collaborative learning environment essential for the success of CBC.

Keywords: Collaboration; Communication; Mental health resources; Online resources; Parental involvement

1. Introduction

The Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) is a transformative educational initiative designed to foster holistic development in learners by emphasizing knowledge, skills and attitudes essential for the 21st century. Implemented to replace the 8-4-4 system in Kenya, the CBC aims to equip students with critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and collaboration skills, aligning with the country's Vision 2030 (Masika, 2020; Mauki et al., 2020). Globally, CBC has demonstrated success in various countries, including the United States, Australia, and Finland, where it has been shown to enhance students' problem-solving abilities, critical thinking skills, and lifelong learning capabilities (Bristow & Patrick, 2014; Halinen et al., 2013; Koo, 2020).

Parental involvement plays a crucial role in the successful implementation of CBC. Research indicates that active parental participation in education, both at home and in school, significantly impacts students' academic success and overall well-being (Brookie, 2021; Piliyesi et al., 2020). Effective parental involvement includes assisting with homework, attending school activities, and maintaining communication with teachers (Schmid & Garrels, 2021; Epstein & Sheldon, 2019). However, despite the recognized importance of parental engagement, challenges such as financial

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constraints, lack of familiarity with the CBC, and time limitations can hinder parents' ability to support their children effectively (Amunga et al., 2020; Otieno & Onyango, 2019; Mwarari et al., 2020).

Parental mental health is a critical factor influencing the effectiveness of CBC implementation. The transition to CBC has introduced new demands and costs, which can exacerbate stress and strain on parents, affecting their mental well-being (Hall, 2021; Nsengimana, 2021). Financial instability, especially heightened during external crises like the COVID-19 pandemic, further compounds these challenges, leading to increased anxiety and stress among parents (Skandar et al., 2022; Ajuoga & Keta, 2021). The expectation for parents to balance professional and personal responsibilities while actively engaging in their children's education can be overwhelming, impacting their ability to provide the necessary support (Gitahi, 2019; Kuria, 2022). While the CBC aims to revolutionize education and prepare students for future challenges, its success heavily relies on active and effective parental involvement. It is imperative for schools and policymakers to address the barriers parents face and provide the necessary support systems to enhance parental engagement. Ensuring the mental well-being of parents is essential, as it directly influences their capacity to support their children's educational journey.

Massucco (2020) conducted a qualitative inquiry exploring the perspectives of parents, teachers, and administrators regarding parental involvement and parent-school partnership strategies among middle school students in a Georgia middle school. The study suggests reassessing parental involvement strategies to identify innovative approaches that enhance engagement and academic achievement, aiming to reduce disparities among socioeconomic groups. The study's findings highlight the importance of evaluating and updating parental involvement strategies to ensure they effectively address the needs of all students, particularly those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. By identifying and implementing innovative approaches, schools can foster greater parental engagement, which is crucial for enhancing students' academic success and overall well-being.

Wongthong and Noiwong (2023) conducted a mixed-method study in Thailand to explore the nuances, requirements, and guidelines for implementing a competency-based curriculum (CBC) in public primary schools. Data from 99 school directors and 316 teachers highlighted the need for preparatory measures and collaborative efforts among administrators, teachers, parents, and stakeholders. The study emphasized the importance of coaching, mentoring, and professional development initiatives to promote collaborative learning and continuous improvement.

Levinthal et al. (2021) conducted a qualitative investigation focusing on Finnish and Portuguese parents' perspectives on teachers' roles in fostering parent-teacher partnerships and enhancing parental engagement with schools. The study involved interviews with 10 Finnish and 9 Portuguese parents, analyzed using inductive content analysis. The research recommended a comprehensive approach to engagement and partnerships within teacher education, including consistent but straightforward communication with parents and reassessing the frequency of parental activities within the school environment.

Careemdeen (2024) investigated parental involvement in secondary education in Sri Lanka, examining how parental income and gender affect involvement levels. The study stressed enhancing parental education and awareness to address income-based disparities in involvement, aiming for more equitable educational outcomes. The findings highlight the importance of informed and engaged parents in promoting educational equity and recommend targeted efforts to increase parental involvement, especially in underprivileged communities, to ensure all students benefit from active parental support.

Ma (2022) examined Chinese parents' perspectives on their involvement in their children's elementary education (ages 6-12) through semi-structured interviews with ten parents. The study highlighted various dimensions of parental involvement, including understanding, motivations, challenges, impacts, specific behaviors, and expectations. Parents recognized their involvement as crucial for their children's academic performance, cognitive development, behavioral habits, and mental and psychological well-being, emphasizing its necessity. Effective behaviors identified included maintaining a harmonious parent-child relationship, high-quality companionship, assistance in developing behavioral habits, and support for emotional and psychological development. Parents stressed equality, respect, quality time, independence, and emotional understanding. They noted the profound impact of their involvement on their children's development.

Schmid and Garrels (2021) studied parental involvement and its impact on educational success among vulnerable students in vocational education and training. With a sample of 25 participants from families with limited socioeconomic resources, semi-structured interviews were transcribed and analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis. The study highlighted the importance of identifying resources available to parents from diverse backgrounds and

emphasized collaborative approaches between schools and families to empower parents in supporting their children's education.

Assey (2022) conducted a case study to explore strategies for enhancing the implementation of the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Tanzanian secondary schools. The study involved 112 participants, including District Education Officers, Quality Assurers, heads of secondary schools, and teachers. Data were collected through focus groups and interviews and analyzed thematically. The findings emphasized the importance of fostering effective partnerships between schools and parents to achieve successful CBC implementation. The study highlights the critical role that collaboration between schools and parents plays in the effective rollout of the CBC. The research underscores the necessity of creating robust partnerships and clear communication channels to support the CBC's objectives. By focusing on these partnerships, the study advocates for strategies that enhance parent-school interactions, in the long run contributing to a more successful implementation of the CBC framework.

Abraha (2022) examined family involvement in schooling at Selam Elementary School in Ethiopia using grounded theory. The study employed purposive sampling with parents and principals as participants, and data were collected through interviews and focus group discussions, analyzed using open, axial, and selective coding. The findings revealed significant shortcomings in mobilizing parental involvement and highlighted the need for improved collaboration between teachers and parents to address students' instructional challenges. The research highlights the crucial need for stronger family-school partnerships and advocates for enhanced collaboration between parents and teachers, emphasizing that effective communication and cooperation are essential for addressing instructional challenges and supporting student success. This call for improved teacher-parent collaboration encourages schools to develop more inclusive strategies to foster active parental involvement.

Muchira et al. (2023) investigated Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) models in the United States and South Korea to provide insights for improving CBC implementation in Kenya. By conducting a scoping review of peer-reviewed articles, the study highlighted valuable lessons and strategies applicable to the Kenyan context. The researchers recommended addressing implementation challenges by leveraging evidence and aligning goals at various levels of the education system. The study offers a comparative perspective that underscores the importance of learning from international CBC models. The researchers emphasize that adopting evidence-based strategies and ensuring alignment across different educational levels can significantly enhance CBC implementation in Kenya. Their findings suggest that a careful adaptation of successful practices from other countries, combined with a thorough understanding of local challenges, can lead to more effective implementation and better educational outcomes. This approach not only provides practical recommendations for policymakers and educators but also contributes to a more informed and evidence-driven strategy for the CBC's success in Kenya.

Waruingi et al. (2022) assessed the challenges faced by principals in implementing the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in public primary schools in Kiambu County, Kenya. Through an inductive thematic content design and the purposive sampling of 15 principals and 15 deputies, the study highlighted the critical need for targeted training and sensitization of parents regarding CBC changes. The researchers emphasized the importance of fostering community engagement and collaboration among stakeholders to effectively address resource needs. This findings reflect a broader understanding of the complexities involved in CBC implementation and advocate for a concerted effort to involve all relevant parties in the process. This approach aims to enhance the overall effectiveness of CBC programs by ensuring that both educational leaders and the community are well-prepared and actively engaged.

Mwarari et al. (2020) focused on parental involvement in CBC implementation in Kenya, highlighting perceived challenges and opportunities. Recommendations included developing comprehensive policy guidelines to direct parental roles in the partnership, institutionalizing parental involvement at the school level, and creating strategies for enhancing teacher-parent engagement. The study also emphasized the need for parent-teacher organizations to adapt their roles to align with CBC demands, advocating for friendly relationships and informal activities to strengthen family-school connections.

Syomwene (2022) observed that insufficient time is dedicated to acknowledging the role of parents in student learning during teacher training, which poses challenges for new teachers in engaging with parents effectively. The study highlights the need for more comprehensive training programs that emphasize the importance of parental involvement in education. To address this gap, the researcher recommends increasing capacity-building seminars for teachers and organizing parental awareness seminars to better equip educators and foster stronger parent-teacher partnerships. The study highlights the need for improved training and awareness programs to better prepare teachers for working with parents. By advocating for increased capacity-building seminars for teachers and parental awareness sessions, the

research aims to enhance collaboration between teachers and parents, thereby supporting a more effective educational environment.

Njeru and Kirimi (2023) suggested that private schools should allocate additional time for interacting with parents to enhance awareness about the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) implementation. Their recommendation emphasizes the need to clearly inform parents about their roles and address any misconceptions they may have regarding the CBC. By doing so, the researchers aim to ensure that parents are well-informed and actively engaged in the educational process. In a similar vein, Mogere and Mbataru (2023) recommended the introduction of diaries in public schools to facilitate daily interactions between parents and teachers. This initiative is intended to improve communication and provide a structured way for parents to stay updated on their children's progress. The researchers argue that such a system can enhance parental involvement and support the effective implementation of educational programs. These studies collectively highlight the importance of enhancing communication and engagement strategies between schools and parents. They advocate for practical measures that can bridge gaps in understanding and collaboration, ultimately supporting better educational outcomes.

Wambua and Waweru (2019) investigated the constraints associated with implementing the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Machakos County, Kenya, using a descriptive survey design. Their study identified several challenges and recommended organizing targeted campaigns to sensitize parents and other stakeholders about their roles in the CBC implementation process. The researchers advocate for increased awareness and education among all involved parties, highlighting that effective communication and understanding of roles are essential for overcoming implementation challenges. Their findings underscore the need for proactive efforts to engage and inform stakeholders, ensuring a smoother transition to the CBC framework and enhancing its overall effectiveness.

Piliyesi et al. (2020) explored the critical role of parental involvement in the processes of curriculum adoption, implementation, and evaluation. The study emphasizes the need for enhanced parental engagement through shared responsibilities, targeted training, and appropriate incentives. The researchers advocate for strengthening school-parent partnerships and recognizing the valuable contributions of parents. Their findings highlight that fostering effective collaborations between schools and families is essential for successful curriculum development and implementation. By focusing on these areas, the study calls for a more integrated approach to involving parents in educational processes, which can significantly enhance the effectiveness and responsiveness of curriculum initiatives.

Waswa (2020) examined parental involvement in pre-primary pupils' access to and transition into primary school education in Kakamega County, Kenya. Utilizing Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems model and a survey design, the study found that parental involvement in supporting activities was notably low. The researcher underscores the need for targeted strategies to improve engagement, including increased sensitization efforts and more regular communication about children's progress. This findings highlight the importance of enhancing parental involvement to support smoother transitions and better educational outcomes for young learners. This focus on addressing gaps in parental engagement serves as a crucial call for action to ensure that parents are more actively involved in their children's educational journey from the early stages.

Addressing the barriers to effective parental participation and supporting the mental well-being of parents are crucial steps in ensuring a smooth transition to this innovative educational framework. By adopting comprehensive strategies to enhance parental involvement and providing robust support systems, schools and policymakers can foster a collaborative educational environment that supports both student success and parental mental health. This study aims to contribute to this endeavor by identifying practical strategies for enhancing parental well-being during CBC implementation, ultimately supporting a more effective and equitable educational experience for all stakeholders involved.

2. Theoretical framework

The study was grounded on Epstein's Parental Involvement Model and Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT). Epstein's model emphasizes collaboration among parents, educators, and the community, focusing on dimensions such as parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration. CBT highlights the impact of parents' thoughts, emotions, and behaviors on their mental health, emphasizing cognitive restructuring, behavioral activation, role modeling, goal setting, and positive reinforcement. Integrating these frameworks provides a comprehensive approach to understanding and improving parental involvement in CBC and its impact on mental well-being, guiding the study's methodology and strategy development.

3. Methodology

The researcher employed a qualitative research approach targeting parents of upper primary learners in public day schools in Nairobi County. Using purposive sampling, 12 participants were selected for the study. Data collection involved detailed interview guides, supplemented by information from libraries and the internet. The data was analyzed thematically and presented in themes. Ethical approval was obtained from the Department of Psychology and the Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences at the Catholic University of Eastern Africa, as well as from the National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI). All participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement in the study.

4. Results

4.1. Sample characteristics

On analysis, the study interviewed 12 participants selected purposefully to reflect a diverse demographic profile. The group comprised 5 males and 7 females, with ages primarily centered around 37 years old. The majority were married, with a notable representation of single individuals, and smaller numbers of divorced and widowed participants. Religious diversity was evident, with Christians making up the majority, alongside Muslims and Hindus. Education levels varied, with several participants holding tertiary education backgrounds, potentially influencing their perspectives on CBC. Occupationally, participants were employed across different sectors, which affected their availability, perspectives on education, and financial resources for supporting their children's education.

4.2. Findings

The analysis identified several key themes that reveal the influence of CBC strategies on parents' mental health and their overall experience.

The initial item focused on participants' opinions regarding the actions schools should take to assist and support parents during the implementation of CBC. Themes that emerged were: workshops, resources, communication and collaboration.

Workshops: Participants expressed the need for guidance regarding CBC. They believe workshops and training sessions tailored for parents would be beneficial, providing them with the tools to effectively support their children's learning. They suggested that schools organize workshops to explain the CBC curriculum and how parents can complement their children's learning at home. They mentioned:

"We want to be there for our kids, but sometimes we need a little guidance, especially when it comes to new teaching methods. Workshops and training sessions for parents are a fantastic idea. They equip us with the tools we need to support our children's learning effectively." (Participant L03, Personal Communication, November 29, 2023).

"The competence-based curriculum might be new to many of us, and we want to make sure we're doing the right things at home to complement what they're learning at school. Workshops can bridge that gap and boost our confidence." (Participant L08, Personal Communication, December 18, 2023).

"Schools could organize workshops specifically for parents, explaining the CBC curriculum and how we can reinforce the learning at home." (Participant L11, Personal Communication, December 28, 2023).

Resources: Participants also exposed the need for schools to put additional materials available online which may be helpful for parents looking to engage more in their child's competency-based curriculum (CBC) learning. The responses from the participants were as follows:

"Creating online resources or a platform where parents can access supplementary materials related to CBC topics would be great." (Participant L05, Personal Communication, December 06, 2023).

"Having access to materials that align with the curriculum can be a game-changer. It allows us to engage with our kids in a meaningful way and reinforce their learning." (Participant L07, Personal Communication, December 13, 2023).

"Online courses are a great idea too. They provide flexibility for parents who may have busy schedules. We can learn at our own pace and revisit the material when we need it. It's all about making it easier for us to be active partners in our children's education." (Participant L011, Personal Communication, December 28, 2023).

Communication: The participants also suggested that there need for schools should establish open and consistent channels of communication with parents. Participants commented these ways:

"Regular communication from teachers regarding curriculum changes or new teaching methods would be incredibly helpful." (Participant L01, Personal Communication, November 20, 2023).

"Schools need to improve communication with parents. Sometimes, I feel like I'm in the dark about what's happening in my child's education." (Participant L04, Personal Communication, December 01, 2023).

"It's frustrating when you hear about changes or events from other parents or when it's too late. An accessible school website with all the important information would be fantastic. We're in the digital age, and this would make our lives so much easier." (Participant L08, Personal Communication, December 18, 2023).

"It would make us feel more involved in our children's education when we know what's going on, we can better support them at home. It's a win-win situation." (Participant L09, Personal Communication, December 22, 2023).

"To schools, we say thank you for recognizing the importance of parental involvement and for offering these opportunities. When we're well-informed and equipped, our children benefit, and their educational journey becomes even more rewarding." (Participant L11, Personal Communication, December 28, 2023).

Collaboration: Participants also raised the need for increased interaction through sessions or open houses to discuss CBC-related matters. One expressed:

"Offering parent-teacher sessions or open houses to discuss CBC methods and its impact on our children's learning." (Participant L08, Personal Communication, December 18, 2023).

The second item involved participants' perspectives on what actions parents should take to support themselves during the implementation of CBC. Themes that were revealed include: Community support, facilitation, provision of mental health resources and access to Counseling Services.

Community support: Participants also suggested the establishment of support groups or forums within the parents' association for sharing experiences and resources. Parenting support groups offer a safe space where individuals can share their joys and challenges without fear of judgment. Through open and honest discussions, parents can receive validation for their experiences and find comfort in the understanding and empathy of fellow group members. These interactions foster a supportive community where parents can feel heard and supported. Participants provided feedback in the following manners:

"We could establish support groups within the parents' association where we share tips, resources, and experiences related to supporting CBC learning at home." (Participant L05, Personal Communication, December 06, 2023).

"For those of us who are neighbors, we can pool together resources." (Participant L07, Personal Communication, December 13, 2023).

"Initiating fundraisers or drives to provide learning materials or technology for families who might struggle to afford resources." (Participant L10, Personal Communication, December 27, 2023).

One participants valued the involvement of community organizations in providing mental health resources but emphasized the need for sustained support rather than infrequent events. He remarked:

"Community seminars on mental health might be enlightening. It' would be great to see the school partnering with local organizations to provide these resources. It needs to be an ongoing support rather than one-time events. Continuous engagement could make a bigger impact." (Participant L08, Personal Communication, December 18, 2023).

Facilitation: Participants suggested the need of bringing in experts or organizing talks to guide parents in supporting CBC learning. Participants had the following to say:

"Organizing seminars or talks by experts to guide us in effectively engaging with our children's CBC education." (Participant L03, Personal Communication, November 29, 2023).

"Creating a platform or social media group where parents can exchange ideas and ask questions about CBC learning strategies." (Participant L06, Personal Communication, December 12, 2023).

Provision of mental health resources: The significance of parental mental health in a child's education cannot be overstated. Some participants expressed significant relief and benefit from attending stress management workshops. One participant shared,

"Attending the stress management workshops has been incredibly beneficial for me. I learned practical techniques to manage my anxiety and stress, which has made a huge difference in how I support my child with their CBC assignments. The workshop leader was very understanding of our unique challenges as parents." (Participant L07, Personal Communication, December 13, 2023).

Access to Counseling Services: Many participants emphasized the importance of having access to counseling services. The participants remarked:

"The transition to the CBC is challenging for most of us. Having access to free counseling services can be a lifesaver. The counselor may help us navigate our feelings of overwhelm and frustration." (Participant L02, Personal Communication, November 23, 2023).

"It would be reassuring to know that counselling support is available when we need it." (Participant L07, Personal Communication, December 13, 2023).

"Tailored mental health support specifically for CBC parents is crucial. General parenting advice isn't as effective because it doesn't address the unique aspects of the CBC." (Participant L09, Personal Communication, December 22, 2023).

The final element centered on participants' viewpoints on the actions learners should take to assist and support their parents during the implementation of CBC. Themes that emerged were: communication, responsibility, fostering independence, empowerment and appreciation.

Communication: Participants encouraged open communication between parents and learners. The participants made the following statements:

"Our children can communicate more about what they are learning and how we parents can assist them without feeling overwhelmed." (Participant L02, Personal Communication, November 23, 2023).

"They can communicate more about what they are learning and how we parents can assist them without feeling overwhelmed." (Participant L05, Personal Communication, December 06, 2023).

"We would appreciate it if our CBC children could communicate openly about their schoolwork and any challenges they're facing. This way, we can offer assistance or seek help from teachers if needed. Being informed helps us to support them better." (Participant L09, Personal Communication, December 22, 2023).

Responsibility: It is a responsible and considerate behavior for children to take care of the learning resources their parents provide for them and to reuse them when possible. By taking care of these resources, children show appreciation for the investment their parents make in their education. A participant expressed the desire for their child to take care of materials that can be reused. She conveyed:

"It would be really helpful if our CBC child could understand the importance of budgeting and saving. Take care the necessary materials that could be reused. This would ease our burden." (Participant L12, Personal Communication, December 28, 2023).

Fostering independence: Competence-based curricula often emphasize self-directed learning and independence. A participant highlighted the necessity for learners to proactively organize study groups with their classmates. He expressed:

"Taking responsibility for their own learning by organizing study groups with classmates." (Participant L02, Personal Communication, November 23, 2023).

Empowerment: Children can act as peer educators, sharing their knowledge and expertise with their parents. Teaching others reinforces their own understanding and mastery of digital tools and platforms, while also fostering a sense of responsibility and accomplishment. Participants also pointed out that children can assist their parents in understanding the digital tools or platforms utilized in CBC education. They said:

"Helping us parents understand the digital tools or platforms they use for learning, so we feel more comfortable assisting them." (Participant L04, Personal Communication, December 01, 2023).

"Our children are faster than us in understanding this digital world. It will be effective if they assist us parents understand the digital tools or platforms they use for learning, so we feel more comfortable assisting them." (Participant L07, Personal Communication, December 13, 2023).

"Our children are practically experts in latest technology gadgets. They need to support us on how to use them as we tackle some of their home assignments." (Participant L10, Personal Communication, December 27, 2023).

Appreciation: Parents play a significant role in providing guidance, encouragement, and resources for their children's education. Expressing gratitude towards parents for their support can strengthen the parent-child bond and acknowledge the efforts parents make to ensure their children have the opportunity to learn and grow. Showing appreciation can also motivate parents to continue supporting their children's education and foster a positive family dynamic centered on learning and achievement. Participants also proposed that learners can contribute to a positive and supportive learning environment by expressing gratitude and acknowledging the efforts their parents invest in supporting CBC education. One conveyed:

"Expressing gratitude and acknowledging the efforts we as parents make in supporting the CBC education." (Participant L01, Personal Communication, November 20, 2023).

5. Discussion

The findings reveal critical insights into how parental support can be enhanced during CBC implementation, emphasizing the need for workshops, resources, communication, and collaboration from schools. These findings align with existing literature on parental involvement and educational strategies. The study underscores the necessity for workshops and training sessions aimed at guiding parents through the CBC framework. Literature supports this need, with scholars like Yungungu and Rodgers (2022) emphasizing the importance of parental sensitization programs to enhance involvement in children's education. Similarly, Wairimu (2020) advocates for parenting and family support programs that go beyond homework assistance. The integration of Epstein's Parental Involvement Model suggests that structured workshops can address the gaps in parental knowledge and confidence, thereby fostering a more supportive educational environment (Epstein et al., 2009). The study also highlights the demand for accessible online resources and materials aligned with the CBC. This finding resonates with Schmid and Garrels (2021), who emphasize the importance of providing diverse resources to cater to different parental needs. Ngina (2024) further supports this by recommending the establishment of online platforms to facilitate parental engagement. Providing such resources helps bridge the information gap and empowers parents to support their children's learning effectively. Effective communication between schools and parents is crucial, as indicated by the participants' feedback. Levinthal et al. (2021) advocate for maintaining regular and straightforward communication to enhance parental involvement. The study's findings are consistent with this view, highlighting that clear, timely updates about curriculum changes and teaching methods can significantly impact parental engagement and support. The need for increased collaboration through sessions or open houses aligns with recommendations from Waruingi et al. (2022), who emphasize the value of stakeholder cooperation in addressing educational needs. Collaborative efforts among parents, educators, and administrators can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, which is essential for the successful implementation of CBC. Participants expressed the need for community support groups and mental health resources. This reflects the broader need for systemic support structures, as noted by Leger et al. (2022), who highlight the role of support groups in providing emotional and practical assistance to parents. Alemu et al. (2023) further support this by emphasizing the benefits of psychoeducational workshops in improving mental health literacy and family relationships. Providing consistent mental health resources and counseling services can mitigate the stress associated with CBC implementation, fostering a more supportive environment for parents (Goldberg et al., 2019). The study also explored how students can support their parents during CBC implementation. Effective communication between parents and learners is vital, as supported by Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997), who suggest that children's articulation of their

educational needs enhances parental involvement. Additionally, encouraging students to take responsibility for their learning resources and fostering independence aligns with the principles of competence-based education, promoting a collaborative learning environment (Pale & Amukowa, 2020).

The findings in the discussion are supported by both Epstein's Parental Involvement Model and Cognitive Behavioral Theory. The Epstein's Parental Involvement Model puts emphasis on workshops and training sessions, accessible resources, effective communication, and collaboration aligns with the dimensions of Epstein's model, which include parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration while the Cognitive Behavioral Theory focuses on mental health resources, counseling services, and the cognitive and behavioral aspects of parental involvement in CBC implementation resonates with CBT principles, which highlight cognitive restructuring, behavioral activation, role modeling, goal setting, and positive reinforcement. These strategies aim to improve parents' mental health and well-being, which is a core tenet of CBT.

6. Conclusion

Parents' mental well-being is positively influenced when they are well-informed and actively engaged in their children's education. These findings underscore the necessity for schools and policymakers to adopt strategies that enhance parental involvement and provide robust support systems.

Recommendations

The study recommends that schools provide continuous mental health resources and enhance communication between schools and parents. Offering mental health resources and counseling services tailored specifically for CBC parents can help manage the stress and anxiety associated with the curriculum transition, thereby improving parents' mental well-being. In parallel, establishing clear and consistent communication channels, such as regular updates through newsletters, school websites, and digital platforms, ensures that parents are well-informed about curriculum changes and teaching methods.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The study was approved by the Catholic university of Eastern Africa, Department of Psychology ethical committee.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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